

Combined effects of WC and SiC on densification and thermo-mechanical stability of ZrB₂ ceramics

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ABSTRACT

ZrB₂-based mixtures containing WC and SiC in various amounts were hot-pressed at 1930°C, achieving final relative densities above 94%. The diboride matrix of the sintered ceramics was constituted by (Zr,W)B₂ solid solution shells grown onto original ZrB₂ grains. WC phase reacted during sintering leaving W-monoboride and mixed Zr,W-carbide as secondary phases. Room temperature flexure strength ranged from 540 to 630 MPa, but performances of major significance were determined at 1500°C in air, with values exceeding 700 MPa. SiC was vital to improve the oxidation resistance at 1500°C compared to SiC-free ZrB₂-based ceramic. W, encased in the shell, retarded the inward diffusion of oxygen compared to the pure ZrB₂.

Keywords: ZrB₂, tungsten, solid solution, mechanical properties, oxidation.

1. Introduction

Zirconium diboride (ZrB₂) belongs to the well-known class of compounds conventionally named as ultra-high temperature ceramics (UHTCs), because of their melting point above 3000°C. Research activity of recent years has been addressed to continuously improve its thermo-mechanical capabilities, failure tolerance, and ablation/oxidation resistance through the tailored addition of various secondary phases [1-5].

SiC has been repeatedly added in a range of 5-30 vol% to transition metal diborides (MeB₂), owing to its proven ability to help densification of MeB₂, as well as to limit the growth rate of the diboride matrix by pinning the grain boundary migration during the final stage of densification, typically above 1900°C in the case of hot pressing [1,6]. The presence of SiC has also proved to increase flexure strength owing to a refined and dense microstructure [7], as well as the resistance to oxidation up to 1650°C, thanks to the *in-situ* formation of a multi-layered protective oxide scale [8,9].

Additional third phases able to bring benefit to the high temperature performance of MeB₂-SiC systems include carbides and silicides of W, Ta, or Mo [3,10-13]. In this respect, the incorporation of WC has recently gained great attention thanks to an attractive ability claimed by some authors [10,14,15] to favour the flexure strength retention at temperatures up to 1600°C.

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The resistance to oxidation also was reported to take effective advantages from the presence of W-carrying refractory phases inside the resulting microstructure of ZrB₂ ceramics [16-19]. No matter if WC is initially added as second phase [19] or as impurity [7], improved performances at high temperatures were recorded anyways. Average flexure strengths up to 640 MPa at 1600°C in protective Ar atmosphere were achieved as long as a starting quantity of 5 vol% WC was introduced into a ZrB₂-20 vol% SiC powder mix [10]. The potential of the ZrB₂-SiC-WC system has been further disclosed thank to measurements of residual flexure strength (tested at room temperature) after 24 hours of exposure to static air at 1400°C [20]. This material, object of the present work and thereafter designated as ZS15-5WC, despite the adverse influence of 6 vol% residual porosity, lost only 28% of its average room temperature flexure strength, decreasing from 543 to 390 MPa.

As far as the resistance to oxidation is concerned, the beneficial effects to the oxidation rates of ZrB₂ and ZrB₂-SiC ceramics which arise from the presence of tungsten has been already outlined in previous works [10,16-18,21]. The improvement was ascribed to a number of phenomena: i) the occurrence of an eutectic between WO₃ and ZrO₂ at 1275°C activates a liquid phase sintering of the in-situ growing zirconia scale decreasing its porosity [10,16]; ii) the oxidation product WO₃ performs as barrier itself due to the volume increase associated to oxidation of W-species to WO₃ [16]; iii) the incorporation of W atoms in the borate glass increases the stability of the glass itself [17,18].

In this study, we report on advances in the understanding of the densification and oxidation behaviour of W-doped ZrB₂-based ceramics and their thermo-mechanical improvements attained through the addition of refractory carbides such as SiC and WC. The main novelty of this work is related to the achievement of flexure strength values overpassing 700 MPa when tested at 1500°C in air.

2. Experimental procedure

Commercial powders of ZrB₂, SiC and WC (see Table 1) were used to produce three different compositions in the ZrB₂-WC-SiC system. The initial nominal compositions were all based on ZrB₂, with SiC and/or WC as secondary phases in varying amounts, as follows (vol%):

ZS0-15WC: ZrB₂ + 15WC

ZS3-5WC: ZrB₂ + 3SiC + 5WC

ZS15-5WC: ZrB₂ + 15SiC + 5WC

With these three compositions multiple purposes were addressed. ZS0-15WC was designed to keep the system as simple as possible to study the reaction products during sintering. In ZS15-5WC the amount of SiC was set as that typically introduced in the majority of the studies on ZrB₂-SiC [1-3], whilst ZS3-5WC was conceived as optimization of the previous two compositions, in an effort to reduce the amount of SiC phase under the percolation limit, as main responsible of strength decrease at high temperature.

Base component (ZrB_2) and secondary phases (SiC, WC) were weighed in due amounts according to the rule-of-mixture, batched into a PET bottle and then ball-milled for 24 hours in absolute ethanol using SiC milling media. Subsequently the slurries, dried using a rotary evaporator, were sieved through a 150 μ m metallic screen. 30 mm diameter pellets were cold compacted using a uniaxial press with 20 MPa applied pressure. The *green* pellets were directly positioned into the graphite die located inside the vacuum chamber of the hot-press furnace. The inner walls of the graphite die were precautionary protected by a BN-sprayed graphitized 0.5 mm thick foil. The pellets were thus hot-pressed in the vacuum range of 0.1-1 mbar using an induction-heated graphite die and applying a constant uniaxial pressure of 30 MPa during ramping up to 1930°C, 15-20°C/min of heating rate. Once the target temperature was reached, the linear pressure was increased up to 40 MPa and maintained up to 35 minutes to promote full densification. The change in thickness (dL) of the *green* pellets under hot pressing was recorded during heating up and final dwell. The experimental dL values were then converted into relative density data, under the hypothesis of a full mass conservation. The temperature was monitored by means of an optical pyrometer focused into a blind hole dug on the external surface of the graphite die. At the end of the final dwell, free cooling followed.

Crystalline phases of the sintered ceramics were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD, mod. D8 Advance - Bruker, Germany). The cell parameters of the secondary phases indexed in the hot-pressed ZrB_2 ceramics were determined using the Rietveld refinement approach. Specific XRD patterns were acquired on a polished surface of a bulk sample, imposing the strongest tabulated ZrB_2 reflections along the 2-theta scanned range of 20°-80° as the internal calibrating known phase. The microstructure of the as-hot-pressed ZrB_2 ceramics were also analyzed on fractured and polished surfaces by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, mod. Σ IGMA, ZEISS NTS GmbH, Germany) coupled to an energy dispersive X-ray micro-analyzer (EDS, mod. INCA Energy 300, Oxford instruments, UK). Key microstructural features like residual porosity, mean grain size and volumetric content of the secondary phases, were evaluated thanks to FESEM micrographs elaborated with the support of the commercial software package Image Pro Plus (v.7, Media Cybernetics, USA).

The bulk densities (ρ_B) of the as-hot-pressed ceramics were measured by Archimedes' method in distillate water at 25°C, while the theoretical densities ($\rho_{TH,0}$) were computed according to the rule-of-phase mixture. Residual porosity was first calculated dividing ρ_B by $\rho_{TH,0}$ and then adjusted/confirmed by scanning electron microscopy inspection on polished sections. The expected final densities ($\rho_{TH,1}$) were updated according to the estimated quantities of the secondary phases. The final relative densities (RD^*) were established according to the image analysis approach.

The 4-pt flexure strength (σ) was measured at room temperature (RT) and at 1500°C in air using the guidelines of the European standards for advanced ceramics ENV843-1:2006 and EN820-1:2002. Chamfered bars with dimensions 25.0 x 2.5 x 2.0 mm³ (length by width by thickness, respectively) were tested at RT

using a semi-articulated steel-made 4-pt fixture (lower span 20mm, upper span 10mm) in a screw-driven load frame (Zwick-Roell mod. Z050, Germany), 1 mm/min of cross-head speed. Flexure strength at high temperature was instead measured using an Instron apparatus (mod. 6025) equipped with a 4-pt fixture made of SiC. Before applying the load during testing at 1500°C, a dwell of 18 min was set to reach thermal equilibrium. For each temperature, at least 3 bars per composition were tested.

The resistance to oxidation was studied using a bottom-loading furnace (Nannetti FC18, Faenza, Italy) exposing rectangular coupons 13.0 x 2.5 x 2 mm³ for 15 minutes to the effects of a stagnant air at 1500°C. The dwell time was chosen on the basis of typical durations of re-entry phase of space shuttles. The coupons, formerly cleaned in acetone and weighed, were bottom-up loaded into the hot zone of the furnace when the target temperature was already achieved, elapsed 15 minutes, and then rapidly down-loaded to allow air-quenching. Post-oxidation changes were first evaluated by calculating the specific mass variation, i.e mass change (Δm) over the exposed initial area (A). The microstructural modifications induced by the oxidation attack were analyzed by XRD and FESEM-EDS analyses on the external oxidized surfaces and fractured cross-sections.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 X-ray diffraction analysis

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the three hot-pressed ZrB₂ ceramics in Figure 1 show the hexagonal ZrB₂ as the dominant phase (hex-ZrB₂, PDF#34-0423). In addition, two other non-stoichiometric phases based on tetragonal tungsten boride (t-WB, PDF#35-0738) and cubic zirconium carbide (c-ZrC, PDF#35-0784) were also indexed, in larger amount for the ZS0-15WC ceramic. Based on the peak intensity ratio, the amount of the tetragonal W-boride does not differ too much in the ZS3-5WC and ZS15-5WC composites, coherently with the same starting WC amount of 5 vol%. On the other hand, residual WC fell below the XRD detection limit and was not indexed in any ceramics object of the present work.

The refined cell parameters of the secondary phases indexed as t-WB and c-ZrC provided evidence of non-negligible deviations from the expected values of the pure standard compounds, as their peaks position shifted to higher 2-theta angles (see Table 2). In accordance with other authors [13,22-25], two solid solutions based on cubic (Zr,W) carbide and tetragonal (W,Zr) boride were supposed to form upon sintering. These secondary phases were interpreted as the products of chemical reactions occurred between the starting secondary phase WC with ZrB₂ particles and the oxygen-bearing species covering their external surface. The presence of a foreign element like W hosted into the cubic ZrC lattice was here confirmed by FESEM-EDS analyses, as commented later in detail. In the case of the tetragonal WB phase, due to very scarce amount of Zr involved, together with an unfavourable overlapping of the characteristic X-

ray signals generated by W and Zr, the capture of Zr into the t-WB lattice was considered sound and very probable, but in the need of an ultimate quantitative determination.

The major factor affecting the overall volume change of the c-(Zr,W)C and t-(W,Zr)B lattices was attributed to the substitution of W or Zr atoms, 1.42 Å and 1.59 Å of covalent radius respectively, in the respective ideal lattices. As for the c-(Zr,W)C phase is concerned, the replacement of Zr atoms with smaller W ones led the cubic lattice to shrink, Table 2. In the case of the t-(W,Zr)B phase, an anisotropic variation of the cell parameters took place, with a more pronounced expansion of the c-axis compared to the overall contraction of the basal planes, due to the new positioning of covalently larger Zr atoms, Table 2. However, the net effect for the tetragonal cell volume was surprisingly just a slight contraction in the range of 0.2-0.3%. The elemental analysis by FESEM-EDS of the t-(W,Zr)B and c-(Zr,W)C phases is more widely explored in section 3.2.

It should also be considered that the refined cell parameters shown in Table 2 may be affected to some extent by the residual stresses built-up in the sintered bulks upon cooling. The mismatch of the thermal contraction between the primary diboride matrix (7.0 ppm/K [26]) and the secondary phases (3 ppm/K for SiC [27], 7.2 ppm/K for ZrC [27], 6.5 ppm/K for WB [28]) may lead the crystal lattices of all the solid phases to deform: the associated stress state gives rise to measurable shifts of the characteristic planar spacing in the XRD spectra. In fact, taking as example the ZS15-5WC ceramic, where the expected strongest reflections of β -SiC are better defined with no overlapping, the cell parameter of the cubic SiC lattice shrinks of about 0.6% compared to a strain-free state. Thankfully, the thermal expansion mismatch between the diboride matrix and c-(Zr,W)C or t-(W,Zr)B does not differ appreciably, thus the calculated shifts of the cell volume, as shown in Table 2, can be fully attributed to composition variation of the stoichiometric t-WB and c-ZrC phases.

3.2 Microstructure analysis by FESEM-EDS

A feature common to all the as-sintered ZrB₂ ceramics is the distinct morphology of the diboride matrix. In detail, ZrB₂ grains developed a round and regular shape associated to a sub-structure, widely known as “*core-rim*”. Such sub-structure consists of stoichiometric ZrB₂ nuclei, i.e. cores, surrounded by a isostructural (Zr,W)B₂ solid solution which constitutes the rims, as exemplified in Fig. 2. The “*core-rim*” feature is well developed throughout the bulk, much more pronounced in ZS0-15WC material for which the peculiar feature of the rim tends to take a continuous network likeness. The amount of W captured into the rims was investigated by FESEM-EDS applying low voltage to the primary electron beam in order to confine the excited X-ray generation volume just underneath the rim under analysis. Several FESEM-EDS measurements revealed a W content in the (Zr,W)B₂ solid solution between 2 and 4 at% with respect to Zr. Concerning the new secondary phases formed, FESEM-EDS analyses could only confirm representative compositions ranges of (W_{1-x}Zr_x)B and (Zr_{1-y}W_y)C, where 0.02 ≤ x ≤ 0.04, 0.13 ≤ y ≤ 0.15. The actual expected

density ($\rho_{TH,1}$) of the hot-pressed ceramics were then refined using the following theoretical density for t-(W,Zr)B and c-(Zr,W)C, 15.52 ± 0.08 and 7.50 ± 0.06 g/cm³, respectively, in conjunction to their volumetric estimates obtained via image analysis. The theoretical density of the aforementioned secondary phases was calculated applying the elemental composition estimated by FESEM-EDS to the refined cell volume in Table 2 obtained via the Rietveld approach.

These findings, together with the formation of secondary phases, like (Zr,W)C and (W,Zr)B, demonstrate that WC is not stable across the processed temperature range, but actively interacted not only with the ZrB₂ matrix, but also with its native oxide impurities, absent indeed in the final microstructure. Similar conclusions were drawn for other sintering additives used for ZrB₂ or HfB₂, like the disilicides of Zr, Hf, Ta, Mo and W [3,19], or other W-based compounds [23]. The assessment of the regular shape of the diboride matrix is of great value, because it can be linked to specific mechanisms of mass transport during densification, as discussed later on. FESEM-EDS analyses did not allow to assess in a robust manner the eventual capture of minor content of B or C into the lattice of c-(Zr,W)C or t-(W,Zr)B phases, respectively, due to the in-situ electron beam activated carbon contamination together with a strong overlapping of the excited characteristic peaks of interest for the desired analysis.

3.2.1 The ZS0-15WC ceramic

The microstructure of this ZrB₂ ceramic, depicted in Fig. 3a, shows that the different phases are homogeneously distributed and no large defects can be seen. The mean grain size of the diboride matrix is 1.6 μ m and 19.5 vol% W-containing secondary phases were estimated, thanks to a brighter appearance compared to the grey background associated to the diboride based matrix. Based on the image analysis estimates, 13.9 vol% (characterized by a white smooth appearance in Fig. 3b) was attributed to (W,Zr)B, whilst 5.8 vol% (featured with a greyer contrast in Fig. 3b) to (Zr,W)C. It is essential repeating that these secondary phases in such amounts, as well as the extensive formation of rims surrounding ZrB₂ cores cannot merely be explained in term of reactions occurring during hot pressing between WC and the oxygen-bearing species of ZrB₂, but ought to be illustrated through a direct role of the ZrB₂ matrix itself. Only in the present case, due to the well-developed distinction between cores and rims, it was possible to estimate a core-to-rim volumetric ratio of 70 to 30 vol%. Very rarely WC with oxygen traces, distinguishable thanks to a rough bright appearance, was also found. In addition, 3 vol% residual free C is present scattered throughout the bulk, with a dark and elongated shape (see Fig. 3b). The C residue, as well as (W,Zr)B and (Zr,W)C, contribute to compose the bulk density, and make the *RD* value in Table 3 underestimated. According to the volumetric amount of primary and secondary phases in the hot-pressed ceramic, the re-calculation of the expected pore-less density, $\rho_{TH,1} = 7.37 \pm 0.02$ g/cm³ does not differ appreciably from the measured one, 7.11 ± 0.01 g/cm³. The ceramic results indeed fully compact and no fine closed porosity in measurable amount was seen during FESEM inspection.

3.2.2 The ZS3-5WC ceramic

FESEM images in Figure 3c,d reveal a uniform and fully dense microstructure with regularly featured grains of the diboride matrix, 1.8 μm as mean size. The secondary phases are homogeneously distributed. SiC phase was estimated to occupy 2.8 vol% of the available volume: from this finding the authors are inclined to attribute a minor role to SiC in the chemical reactions occurred during hot pressing that led the resulting microstructure to change significantly compared to the nominal one. In fact, 5 vol% initial WC evolved into new 6.3 vol% W-containing phases, together with 0.6 vol% of free C. The peculiar “core-rim” feature of the diboride matrix was clearly confirmed. The re-calculation of the expected density $\rho_{TH,1}$ was $6.45 \pm 0.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$. SiC phase occasionally showed a core-rim sub-structure with the rim containing Zr traces. The overall role of SiC during hot-pressing is explained in the section 3.3.

3.2.3 The ZS15-5WC ceramic

The representative microstructure of this ceramic is shown in Fig. 3e,f. Differently from ZS0-15WC and ZS3-5WC, the ZS15-5WC did not reach full density, and about 6 vol% of residual porosity was observed via FESEM inspection of the polished surface. The mean grain size of the diboride matrix, 1.5 μm , was in the same range as the previous materials, as reported in Table 3, and the distribution of the secondary phases was confirmed homogeneous. Macro-defects or large agglomerates were not seen by FESEM. The image analysis expressed an estimate of 14.7 vol% for SiC and 7.5 vol% for W-containing secondary phases. Investigating the microstructure in thorough detail, the phases already identified in the previous ceramics were once more confirmed. A finer segmentation of the grey levels enabled to discriminate between (W,Zr)B and (Zr,W)C, and 3.5 and 4.0 vol% were set as best estimates. However, the residual free C remained undetermined owing to the widespread residual porosity featured in the FESEM micrograph with an equivalent black appearance, making the ultimate grey level segmentation for free C unsuccessful. Based on the previous findings in ZS0-15WC and ZS3-5WC ceramics, a guess of 1 vol% residual free C was supposed being formed also in ZS15-5WC material and hence used to recalculate $\rho_{TH,1}$, which resulted $6.03 \pm 0.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$.

3.3 Densification behavior

Looking at the relative density (*RD*) data summarized in Table 3 it might be inferred that the hot-pressed compositions achieved a relative density above 92%. Now, the theoretical density $\rho_{TH,0}$ was calculated according to the rule-of-mixture based on the only nominal starting composition. The microstructure analyses by XRD and FESEM-EDS described in Sections 3.1-3.2 proved in a robust manner that the post-sintering compositions changed significantly compared to the starting ones. Taking into

account the estimates of the secondary phases via image analysis, the expected final densities, $\rho_{TH,1}$, were therefore re-calculated (see Table 3).

Except for ZS15-5WC, the conditions adopted during hot pressing conducted the ZS0-15WC and ZS3-5WC powder mixtures to achieve full density. The linear shrinkage (dL) recorded during the hot press runs were elaborated under the assumption of the mass conservation, and converted into the relative density (RD^*) vs. temperature/time plots (see Fig. 4). Under the same effect of 30 MPa applied pressure, the composition that started to shrink at lower temperature (T_{ON}) was ZS3-5WC (1550°C) followed by ZS0-15WC (1630°C) and ZS15-5WC, for which a measurable shrinkage of the sample thickness started taking place only at 1740°C, as Figure 4a shows. Considering the materials with the equivalent initial content of 5 vol% WC, ZS3-5WC and ZS15-5WC, the corresponding T_{ON} values suggest that an addition of 15 vol% SiC particles is sufficient to hinder grain-boundary migration during the final stage of sintering, as reported in our previous study [3]. Fig. 4 clearly displays that ZS15-5WC composition had the most sluggish shrinkage rate along the final isothermal dwell, compared to the other two composites containing no or 3 vol% SiC.

The WC phase had unambiguously a dominant role connected to an enhanced temperature reactivity which led it to first react with ZrB_2 and its native oxides and hence disappear in the final ceramic. In fact, it is commonly accepted that a metal diboride MeB_2 powder, $Me=Ti, Zr, Hf$, can restore its intrinsic high temperature sinterability only after having removed the oxygen-carrying species which, covering the external surfaces, passivate the overall chemical reactivity of the pure MeB_2 powder [29]. A series of chemical reactions supposed to be responsible of the oxygen removal from the diboride particle surfaces and consequent formation of some reaction products have been proposed by several authors and are summarized in Table 4 [15,22,23,29]. The minimum temperature (T_{MIN}) over which the Gibbs free energy (ΔG) of a reaction becomes negative was calculated in standard condition of isobaric pressure (1 bar) and in conditions closer to the inner working pressure during hot-pressing (1 mbar). Actually, the amounts of the secondary phases such as $(W,Zr)B$ and $(Zr,W)C$ experimentally estimated via image analysis in the hot-pressed ceramics cannot merely be explained according to reactions in Table 4: the oxygen impurities available for the reactions are not enough to justify the estimated final content of $(W,Zr)B$ and $(Zr,W)C$. It must be thought another driving role for WC that interacts with the diboride matrix: such chemical interactions involve the entire powder mixture and are partially responsible of the formation of $(Zr,W)B_2$, $(W,Zr)B$, $(Zr,W)C$ and free C.

The reaction paths of the primary reactants (ZrB_2 , WC, ZrO_2 , and B_2O_3) were tentatively tracked by means of the thermodynamic solver HSC Chemistry® v. 6.12. Imposing as initial inputs 1 mole of main phases (ZrB_2 and WC) and traces of oxides covering the diboride, 0.1 mole of B_2O_3 and ZrO_2 , it can be read in Fig. 5 that WC is not stable in the conditions imposed during hot pressing: its amount progressively decreases by combining with B_2O_3 and forming the WB phase. Volatile $CO(g)$ is released at the same time. Once the available B_2O_3 is completely consumed, the progressive dissociation of WC yields free W, which is

therefore available during the whole sintering process and can be captured in the boride/carbide solid solutions. The reducing environment favors the formation of ZrC upon removal of ZrO₂ and by following carburization of ZrB₂. The amount of WB keeps increasing with a less steep rate by reacting with ZrB₂ depleted of the native oxide contamination. The reaction path just presented is based on the assumption on specific quantities of only pure compounds. The authors are aware that little variation on one of these parameters can shift equilibria at which specific reactions take place, or local chemistry can trigger competing reactions. Presenting some outputs in Fig. 5 we overall aimed at disclosing through a thermodynamic approach the chemical reactivity of this complex system during sintering which can give rise to new borides and carbides.

Another aspect to consider in the process of densification is the possibility to form liquid phases that could enhance mass transfer mechanisms. Thermodynamic studies in the 60-70' on the mutual stability of compounds in the W-B-C system already verified that the W₂B phase has a very narrow region of homogeneity and is reduced to W metal by Ti, Ta, and Zr, and, in reducing environment, W₂B forms WB, WC and a slight amount of carbon [30]. More recently, the release of W was experimentally verified by Zou and co-authors [23] who heat treated for 1 hour in vacuum at 1650 and 1800°C a mixture of WC and ZrO₂; W₂B can be seen as a by-product for the final W. Unfortunately, the eventual formation of another by-product like WB₂ couldn't be taken into account because not included in the available HSC Chemistry's database.

Eutectic temperatures in the W-B binary system are foreseen from 1930 to 2600°C, being the lowest between WB₁₂ and B [31]. Nevertheless, the contemporary introduction of multiple elements like Zr, Si, C and O into the W-B system can further decrease the temperature at which melts form [32] and promote the formation of a transient liquid phase (TLP) at much lower temperature, above T_{ON} . The term "liquid" is here borrowed for sake of clarity from an accepted terminology referable to the sintering of advanced ceramics. Now, the actual fluidity of TLP during HP upon its onset is here only matter of speculation. Much more important is its own transient nature: in fact the TLP disappeared upon cooling, leaving as its most tangible signature the core/rim sub-structure. In any case, such TLP is here designated as the main carrier capable of moving atoms through the grain boundaries to feed the diffusion-solution/re-precipitation mechanism active during HP and therefore the overall densification process. It is the present authors' belief that such an extensive formation of core-rim sub-structures throughout the sintered bulk must be interpreted claiming an extended mass transfer during hot-pressing sustained by the TLP which led the ZS0-15WC and ZS3-5WC compositions to fully densify.

As for the role of SiC particulate inside WC-containing ZrB₂-based compositions (i.e. ZS3-5WC and ZS15-5WC), some considerations can be drawn. Based on thermodynamic calculations SiC and WC do not react up to 1930°C: the proof is that image analyses, within the accuracy of the method, basically gave back the initially batched quantity. Actually, the silica contamination of SiC, typical of commercial non-oxide

powders (see Table 1), did react with WC and started playing a role during the earliest onset of the TLP formation. Fig. 6 displays the path through which WC and SiO₂ are supposed to start interacting up to their full transformation into W and gaseous species, according to reaction (1) and it appears that W is available at temperature as low as 1130°C.

Increasing the content of SiC (i.e. ZS15-5WC), the yield of W, favorable for sintering, is neutralized by an overall enhanced refractoriness of the ZS15-5WC powder mixture. In the last cited composition, the driving force to eliminate porosity supported by the TLP mechanism was indeed adversely affected by the dragging action of 15 vol% SiC particles which partly pinned the boundaries of the diboride grains without leaving them to migrate away.

3.4 Mechanical properties

The experimental mechanical properties of the ZrB₂ ceramics herein developed are summarized in Table 5 and then compared to published data on ZrB₂-based ceramics initially batched with W-carrying compounds, in form of silicide or carbide [10,19,33].

Amongst the ceramics object of the present study, ZS15-5WC exhibited the lowest room temperature average flexure strength, 543 MPa, primarily owing to 6 vol% residual porosity, while the fully dense ZS3-5WC and ZS0-15WC ceramics exhibited a statistically equivalent mean value, around 630 MPa. When the SiC-free ceramic ZS0-15WC was tested at 1500°C in air, the SiC-made fixture resulted strongly contaminated by a glassy phase exuded by the tested bar, as depicted in Fig. 7. The exuded glassy product was collected and sampled by FESEM-EDS: the analyses revealed the presence of WO₃ with B and C traces. In spite of that, values of great significance were obtained after bending tests at 1500°C in air: the flexure strength retention of ZS0-15WC, ZS3-5WC and ZS15-5WC were 94, 113 and 78% of the RT average values, respectively, see Table 5. From Table 5, a tendency for the high temperature flexure strength behavior can be inferred. Recently, Zou et al. [10] reported that grain sliding and formation of cavities occur preferentially at SiC locations leading to a degradation of the high temperature mechanical performances. Surprisingly, ZS15-5WC, with an overall residual porosity of 6 vol%, resulted in higher strength than a fully dense analogous ceramic initially batched with 5 vol% WSi₂ instead of WC (see composition labeled ZS15-5WS in Table 5). On the other side, the lack of SiC in a fully dense ZrB₂-based matrix enabled to retain the RT values also at 1500°C, although the traumatized appearance of the bar (Fig. 7). In fact, using 15 vol% of solely WSi₂ or WC as starting second phases (ZS0-15WS and ZS015WC, respectively), similar effects on the high temperature flexure strength were recorded, presumably in relation to common features in the sintered microstructures, i.e. the (W,Zr)B phase and a W-enriched rim around ZrB₂ grains. **Worth of mention is also**

the ZS0-15WC ceramic tested at 1500°C in a partially protective Argon environment, unfortunately just one bar was available for this preliminary test, but its flexure strength achieved 715 MPa. Average flexure strength around 710 MPa measured at 1500°C for the ZS3-5WC ceramic was also of notable significance. To the authors' best knowledge, values above 700 MPa were never measured at these temperatures in air. Values of similar significance were reported for ZS20-5WC (see Table 5), although in Argon and using a 3-pt bending configuration. Another confirmation of the potential of the ZrB₂-WC-SiC system to withstand external thermal loads is given by the linearity of the load vs displacement curves at 1500°C during flexure test (not shown), even for ZS15-5WC in presence of a significant amount of SiC and 6 vol% porosity. The preliminary authors' favorite hypothesis to explain the impressive high temperature response of the ZrB₂-WC-SiC relies on the role of the W-enriched rims. Previous investigations by transmission electron microscopy clearly showed that dislocation networks were generated in ZrB₂ grains after bending test at high temperature to progressively accommodate the stress induced by the load [34]. In analogous cases it was assessed that dislocation chains at the core/rim interfaces develop already after sintering upon cooling, owing to the core/rim thermal expansion mismatches [19,35]. The partial absorption of mechanical energy during the flexural test by dislocation flow and multiplication could contribute to the strength retention at high temperature of ZrB₂ ceramics doped with W. An increased dislocations density sets favorable conditions for the creation of dislocation networks, i.e. the creation of sub-grains, resulting in an overall decrease of the flaws size, from the micrometric scale of the original grains, to the nanometric scale of the dislocations tangles [33]. In addition, the achievement of rim-to-rim grain boundaries depleted of foreign oxide compounds, thanks to reactions catalyzed by the addition of WC, also contributes to maintain outstanding flexure strength at high temperature. Dedicate studies on the high temperature strength behavior of this system are currently in progress.

3.5 Oxidation behavior

3.5.1 Mass change, thermodynamics and microstructure modification upon oxidation

The exposure of the sintered ZrB₂ ceramics, with a native grey-dark visual appearance, to an oxidizing environment for 15 min at 1500°C in static air induced a colour change to dark grey, indication of glass formation, or to whitish-yellow, signature of formation of mainly zirconium oxide. The oxidized samples, displayed with representative insets in Fig. 8, look like darker with isolated bubbles when SiC is present, Fig. 8c,e, whilst the resulting aspect of the SiC-free ZS0-15WC specimen is characterized by a yellowish and rough oxide, Fig. 8a. Only in this last case, the external scale detached from the inner un-oxidized substrate and spalled off upon rapid cooling (inset of Fig. 8a).

The specific mass changes are reported in Table 6: the lowest variation, 3.40 ± 0.05 mg/cm², was registered for the material containing 15 vol% SiC (i.e. ZS15-5WC) whilst increasingly larger mass variations were measured for ZS3-5WC (5.35 ± 0.05 mg/cm²) and the SiC-free ZS0-15WC. For this third ceramic, due to

partial detachment of the external oxide scale, the measured mass change, considered not reliable, was not reported in Table 6.

In all cases, the prevailing crystalline phase identified by XRD on the external oxidized surface was indexed as monoclinic ZrO₂, with tetragonal ZrO₂ in traces. Peaks of t-WB, in lower intensities compared to the as-sintered microstructure, were still indexed in ZS3-5WC and ZS15-5WC, i.e. when the silica glass formed on the external surfaces acted as partial inhibitor of the oxygen diffusion into the inner bulk. On the other hand, c-(Zr,W)C and ZrB₂ peaks completely disappeared from the XRD patterns of the three oxidized ceramics. Based on the expression (2):

$$I/I_0 = \exp(-\mu \cdot \rho \cdot \tau) \quad (2)$$

that describes the attenuation intensity (I/I_0) of the initial CuK_α X-ray radiation (I_0 , 30° of glancing angle) at different depth (τ) of a solid specimen with specific density (ρ) and mass attenuation coefficient (μ), scales of 10 μm and 70 μm thick made of only zirconia or silicon oxide, respectively, were calculated being necessary to attenuate 99% of the maximum initial intensity I_0 . It follows that, the characteristic XRD peaks of t-W boride detected in the case of the ZS3-5WC and ZS15-5WC oxidized samples, were generated inside the reaction scale (see Fig. 8d,f), not from the un-oxidized bulk.

The reason of the residual retention of WB in the reaction scale was investigated exploring the thermodynamically favourable reactions of an idealized ZrB₂-SiC-WB-ZrC system progressively attacked by an increasing supply of oxygen. Thermochemical equilibria computed at 1500°C and 1 bar of isobaric pressure revealed that WB is the less inclined phase to react with oxygen, compared to ZrC, ZrB₂ and SiC, Fig. 9a. Most important, at the early stages of the oxidation attack, SiC tends to react with oxygen faster than WB. It follows that WB phase can take advantage from the oxidation of SiC, because the latter phase promptly starts yielding silica glass which protects the inner volume before WB itself begins to oxidize. In the SiC-free ZS0-15WC ceramic, no protection against the inward diffusion of oxygen was afforded by the silica-based glassy coating and the diboride matrix readily transformed into zirconia, which is known to behave only as a moderate barrier to the inward diffusion of oxygen.

In order to free our computations from the variables of input amounts and equilibrium pressure, the predominance diagram is a useful tool to better define stability areas of condensed phases vs temperature and/or chemical potential for selected elemental system, the W-B-O in the present case. Fig. 9b displays that, at 1500°C, metallic W can exist when the oxygen partial pressure is very low, like inside the ZrO₂ grains, whilst, with increasing oxygen partial pressure, the formation of WO₂ and WO₃ is instead favourable.

FESEM images of the external surfaces reported in Fig. 8a,c,e, show that, in absence of SiC, the external oxide scale is wavy and rough, whilst, when 3 or 15 vol% SiC is present, the external surface takes a

smooth glossy appearance because covered by a continuous silica-based glass. White features consisting of zirconia in form of isolated or agglomerated crystals decorate the external glassy coating, Fig. 8c,e.

Representative views of the fractured cross sections of the oxidized samples are shown in Fig. 8b,d,f. As first observation, it can be seen that the absence of SiC led the oxidation front to advance deeper into the inner bulk. The final effect was the creation of an irregular oxide layer, whose representative thickness was estimated to span between 220 and 240 μm , see Table 6. Adding SiC, the ZrB₂ ceramics are much better protected against oxidation at the temperature tested, 1500°C, indicating that a sealing outer glassy scale is more efficient in slowing down the advancement of the oxidation front into the inner bulk, even in presence of 6 vol% of residual porosity, like in the ZS15-5WC ceramic. Indeed, the representative thickness of the modified scale passes from around 80 μm , for 3 vol% of SiC, to 45 μm for 15 vol% of SiC.

In detail, in Fig. 10a, the outermost scale of the ZS15-5WC ceramic is based on silica glass where also traces of W were detected by FESEM-EDS (Fig. 10, spectrum 1). Encased bright contrasting spots are also visible inside the glassy layer which, in turn, is crossed by zirconia pillars outcropping the external surface. Underneath, rounded zirconia grains with bright discrete pockets of the native partially oxidized (W,Zr)B can be found, Fig. 10a. Right in this region SiC is no longer present, whilst free C and SiO₂ are formed at its place, Fig. 10b, spectrum 2. Moving inwards and deeper into the bulk, the original SiC particles progressively can be found again with un-oxidized (W,Zr)B.

Throughout the modified scale, moving from the oxide/boride inner front (Fig. 10d) up to the surface (Fig. 10a) rounded nano-sized particles (hereafter indicated as *nano-beads*) of elemental W, or W oxides, with a bright appearance were identified and analyzed (Fig. 10b,c, spectra 3 and 4). Similar “W-O (and possibly Hf) spherical grains” were observed by Carney and co-authors [13] on HfB₂-SiC-WC materials oxidized for 30 min at 1600°C in static air. The yield of elemental W, in the present case frozen as nano-bead upon air quenching, is in agreement with the thermodynamic predictions: based on the outputs in Fig. 9, the oxidation of WB appears one reaction that provides elemental W. Actually, the calculations did not include the diboride rim, i.e. (Zr_{1-x}W_x)B₂, as initial entry and its W entrapped (see Fig. 2) because not present in the available phase database. In essence, the rim is the largest widespread reservoir for W in the hot-pressed microstructure. According to reactions (3-5), W present in the rims is first released as element and subsequently converted into solid/liquid W oxides.

At 1500°C, liquid WO₃ alone, i.e. not embedded into boro-silicate glass, is not stable anymore, but tends to volatilize forming complex gaseous W oxides, like W₃O₉, W₂O₆, W₄O₁₂ and W₃O₈ [36]. On one hand, the lack

of compactness followed by the oxide scale spall off (see Fig. 8) finds its original cause in the extensive release of volatile W oxides. On the other hand, when WO_3 is readily trapped within the (boro)-silicate glass, the disruptive consequences of the evolving W oxide are minimized. The reason why a dense population of W nano-beads survived upon oxidation and fast air quenching is very likely related to their position, well nestled inside ZrO_2 grains where the oxygen partial pressure does not exceed 10^{-8} Pa, see Fig. 9b.

Lastly, the interface between the reaction front and the un-oxidized bulk is regular, well adherent and without cracks, Fig. 10d.

3.5.2 Oxidation mechanism

The main mechanism responsible of the improved oxidation resistance in the ZrB_2 -SiC-WC systems compared to the SiC-deficient one can be purely related to the ability of the in-situ formed external silica-based coating to limit oxygen inward diffusion. $(\text{Zr,W})\text{B}_2$ rims, as well as $(\text{Zr,W})\text{C}$ and $(\text{W,Zr})\text{B}$ phases, are present in the sintered bulk and their resulting oxidation products consist of $\text{ZrO}_2(\text{s})$, $\text{W}(\text{s})$, $\text{WO}_3(\text{l})$ and amorphous $\text{B}_2\text{O}_3(\text{l,g})$. It follows that the glassy silica can change its own composition embedding foreign elements such as Zr, W and B into its glass network. If the availability of W in the silica glass, once modified its actual viscosity, is capable of slowing down the effective diffusion rate of oxygen is still matter of current investigations [33].

Another beneficial mechanism that could take part to the bulk protection against oxidation concerns the modification of the characteristics of the forming zirconium oxide. In the conditions of a reduced oxygen partial pressure, zirconium oxide is known to form and evolve featured by vacancies [37], in a more pronounced density when the reaction front is deep close to the diboride/oxide interface. In this respect, it should be underlined that the base matrix of all these ceramics is characterized by a homogeneously distributed mixed diboride, $(\text{Zr,W})\text{B}_2$, therefore an intimate coexistence of W in the zirconia crystal lattice, at least in the early oxidation stage, very likely took place. The solubility of W in ZrO_2 is very limited, below 2 at% [38], therefore the threshold limit is quickly achieved resulting in the expulsion of W that tends to aggregate as nano-beads across the whole zirconia scale, Fig. 10c. However, the initial presence of guest W cations with higher valence than Zr in the zirconia hosting lattice can act as vacancy filler for the ongoing formation of zirconia deep inside the reaction scale.

Another feature worthy of mention is the formation of a coherent and sharp oxidation front, which has a regular thickness and no cracks are present at the oxide/boride interface, Fig. 8b,d,f. Whilst for other ZrB_2 -based materials, containing Si_3N_4 [39] or other transition metal silicides (Zr, Mo, Ta) [21], the oxidation front proceeded along grain interfaces even in absence of amorphous films, in the present case the diboride grains were entirely attacked trans-granularly, as depicted in Fig. 10d. This behavior was related

once again to the better oxidation resistance of W-containing borides, constituting the adjacent shells of the grains, over pure ZrB_2 , constituting the cores.

4 Conclusions

ZrB_2 ceramics containing varying amount of SiC (0, 3, 15 vol%) and WC (5, 15 vol%) were processed by hot pressing and relative density above 94% were reached. The resulting microstructures were characterized by highly refractory phases, solid solutions and grain junctions depleted of amorphous glassy phases: this enabled to improve the state-of-art of ZrB_2 -ceramics in terms of high temperature capabilities.

The simultaneous addition of SiC (3 vol%) and WC (5 vol%) led the hot-pressed ZrB_2 ceramic to exhibit room temperature average strength of 630 MPa that increased up to 720 MPa upon testing at 1500°C in air. The impressive mechanical response of this system in an oxidizing environment was explained in terms of a combination of favorable conditions:

- i) the extensive formation of core-rim sub-structures, the latter constituted by $(Zr,W)B_2$ solid solutions;
- ii) rim-to-rim grain boundaries depleted of secondary phases;
- iii) the formation of continuous glassy layer upon oxidation at 1500°C, that effectively protected the bulk;
- iv) the presence of WB phase, more oxidation resistant than ZrB_2 , which slowed down oxygen diffusion through grains interfaces.

Finally, the accumulation of dislocations at the core-rim interfaces was indicated as a favorable condition for plastic deformation to accommodate the stress under loading at high temperature which leads the material to retain its thermo-mechanical performances.

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Tables

Table 1: Main characteristics of the starting powders used. ρ_{TH} : theoretical density, d_{50} : median of the granulometric distribution.

Powder	Grade and Supplier	ρ_{TH} (g/cm ³)	d_{50} (μ m)	Purity (wt%)	Main impurities (wt%)
ZrB ₂	Gr. B, H.C. Starck, Germany	6.1	2.1	>98	O:1.5, Hf:0.2
SiC	Gr. BF-12, H.C. Starck, Germany	3.21	0.6	>99	O:0.9
WC	Gr. SD0.5, Treibacher Industries AG, Germany	15.74	0.5	99.5	-

Table 2: Nominal and refined cell parameters ± 1 estimated standard deviation (esd) of the indexed secondary phases through the Rietveld processing approach. V_i : cell volume of the refined structures, $dV_i = (V_i - V_0)/V_0$: cell volume variation with V_0 cell volume of tabulated t-WB and c-ZrC.

Label	Nominal cell parameters		Refined cell parameters			Cell volume			
	t-WB	c-ZrC	t-(W,Zr)B		c-(Zr,W)C	t-(W,Zr)B		c-(Zr,W)C	
	PDF#35-0738	PDF#35-0784	a_1 (Å)	c_1 (Å)	a_1 (Å)	V_1 (Å ³)	dV_1 (%)	V_2 (Å ³)	dV_2 (%)
ZS15-5WC	3.11655, 16.9101	4.6930	3.11034±19	16.923±20	4.6327±3	163.72	-0.32	99.43	-3.80
ZS3-5WC			3.11115±20	16.928±14	4.6228±4	163.88	-0.23	98.79	-4.42
ZS0-15WC			3.11152±32	16.919±21	4.6270±12	163.81	-0.27	99.06	-4.16

Table 3: Initial content of SiC and WC, main hot-pressing (HP) parameters, onset temperature (T_{ON}) of early measurable shrinkage, experimental bulk density ρ_B (± 0.01 g/cm³), theoretical density $\rho_{TH,0}$ and relative density (RD) via rule-of-starting mixture, expected final density $\rho_{TH,1}$ (± 0.02 g/cm³) and relative density (RD^*) set via image analysis, and mean grain size (mgs ± 1 s.d) of diboride matrix.

Label	Initial content (vol%)		HP parameters			T_{ON} (°C)	ρ_B g/cm ³	$\rho_{TH,0}$ (g/cm ³)	RD (%)	$\rho_{TH,1}$ (g/cm ³)	RD^* (%)	Secondary phases by XRD ⁽¹⁾	mgs (μ m)
	SiC	WC	°C	min	MPa								
	ZS0-15WC	0	15	1930	26								
ZS3-5WC	3	5	1930	30	40	1550	6.47	6.50	99.5	6.45	>99.9	t-(W,Zr)B, c-(Zr,W)C, β -SiC	1.8±0.6
ZS15-5WC	15	5	1930	12	40	1740	5.66	6.14	92.2	6.03	93.8	t-(W,Zr)B, c-(Zr,W)C β -SiC	1.5±0.5

⁽¹⁾ Refined cell parameters in Table 2.

Table 4: List of chemical reactions reported in literature; T_{MIN} indicates the temperature at which Gibbs standard free energy (ΔG) becomes negative, 1 bar or 1 mbar isobaric pressure.

Reaction #	Reactants	Products	T_{MIN} (°C) for $\Delta G \leq 0$		Ref.
			1 bar	1 mbar	
1	3 WC + ZrO ₂	ZrC + 3 W + 2 CO(g)	1965	1550	22
2	3 ZrB ₂ + 6 WC + ZrO ₂	6 WB + 4 ZrC + 2 CO(g)	1810	1500	23
3	7 ZrB ₂ + 10 WC + 3 ZrO ₂	10 WB + 10 ZrC + 2 B ₂ O ₃ (g)	2480	2170	
4	2 ZrB ₂ + 5 WC + 3 ZrO ₂	5 ZrC + 5 W + 2 B ₂ O ₃ (g)	2500	2450	15
5	3 WC + B ₂ O ₃	2 WB + W + 3 CO(g)	1510	1230	29
6a	4 WC + B ₂ O ₃	2 WB + W ₂ C + 3 CO(g)	1500	1220	
6b	3 W ₂ C + B ₂ O ₃	2 WB + 4 W + 3 CO(g)	1550	1225	

Table 5: Relative density (RD^*), flexure strength at room temperature (σ_{RT}) and at 1500°C (σ_{1500}) of ZrB₂ ceramics initially batched with WC or WSi₂.

Label	Initial secondary phases (vol%)	RD* (%)	Method	σ_{RT} (MPa)	$\sigma_{1500^\circ C}$ (MPa)	Ref.
ZS0-15WC	15 WC	>99.5	4-pt, air	631±106	596±53	pw
ZS0-15WC			4-pt, Ar	-	715 [#]	
ZS3-5WC	3 SiC, 5 WC	>99.5	4-pt, air	628±76	712±23	
ZS15-5WC	15 SiC, 5 WC	94	4-pt, air	543±41	426±15	
ZS20-5WC	20 SiC, 5 WC	>99	3-pt, Ar	~ 600	~ 650	
ZS0-15WS	15 WSi ₂	>99	4-pt, air	641±19	537±16	19
ZS15-5WS	15 SiC, 5 WSi ₂	>99	4-pt, air	754±104	308±43	33

pw: present work;
[#]only 1 bar tested.

Table 6: Post-oxidation microstructural features of ZrB₂ ceramics after exposure to air at 1500°C for 15 min: specific mass change ($\Delta m/A$), indexed crystalline products by XRD acquired on the surface and indicative thickness of the external silica-based layer (t_1) and of the inner reaction scale (t_2).

Label	$\Delta m/A$ (mg/cm ²) ±0.05	Indexed Crystalline phases by XRD		t_1 (μm)	t_2 (μm)
		Major	Minor		
ZS0-15WC	n.a.	m-ZrO ₂	t-ZrO ₂	-	220-230
ZS3-5WC	5.34	m-ZrO ₂	WB, t-ZrO ₂	5	85
ZS15-5WC	3.40	m-ZrO ₂	WB, t-ZrO ₂	7	45

Figures captions

- Figure 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of the hot-pressed ZrB₂-ceramics: a) ZS0-15WC, b) ZS3-5WC and c) ZS15-5WC.
- Figure 2: FESEM-EDS analysis on the polished section of the ZS15-5WC ceramic showing the core (C) - rim (R) substructures with EDS spectra on the right, as well as SiC particulate (dark area) and W boride (bright area).
- Figure 3: FESEM micrographs of polished sections: (a,b) ZS0-15WC, (c,d) ZS3-5WC, (e,f) ZS15-5WC.
- Figure 4: Relative density (RD^*) vs temperature (T) and vs. dwell time (t) of the composition ZS0-15WC, ZS3-5WC and ZS15-5WC during (a) ramping up to 1930°C and (b) dwelling isothermally up to 35 min.
- Figure 5: Thermo-chemical equilibria calculated at 0.001 bar of isobaric pressure representative of the HP vacuum level and initial moles of starting reactants equal to: 1 ZrB₂, 1 WC, 0.1 ZrO₂ and 0.1 B₂O₃.
- Figure 6: Reaction path vs. temperature of WC (1 mole) and SiO₂ (1 mole) at mbar of isobaric pressure.
- Figure 7: (a) Flight view and (b) lateral view of the SiC-made fixture after bending test in air at 1500°C using bars from the ZS0-15WC ceramic.
- Figure 8: FESEM micrographs from representative areas of (a, c, e) the external surface and (b, d, f) fractured cross section of the ZrB₂ ceramics after oxidation at 1500°C for 15 min. a-b) ZS0-15WC, c-d) ZS3-5WC, e-f) ZS15-5WC. The visual appearance of the coupons upon air-quenching is shown in the insets (upper right corner a, c, e). Reaction scales are also outlined (dotted lines in b, d and f).
- Figure 9: a) Thermo-chemical equilibria calculated at 1500°C, 1 bar of isobaric pressure: starting moles of reactants were 1 ZrB₂, 1 WB, 1 ZrC, and 0.5 SiC. b) Predominance diagram for W-O-B system calculated at 1500°C.
- Figure 10: Details from the fractured cross-section of ZS15-5WC after oxidation at 1500°C showing (a) the morphology of the outermost silica-based layer, b) the consumption of SiC, c) the presence of frozen W nano-beads onto zirconia grains, and d) the coherent growth of zirconia at the diboride/oxide interface. The lower row shows FESEM-EDS spectra acquired on the numbered areas.

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Graphical Abstract